

Tables

Table 1. The location and U-Nd-Sr isotopic compositions of samples in the Tarim Basin

Sample ID	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°E)	$(^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U})$ 2*SE = 0.001	ϵ_{Nd}	2*SE	$^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	2*SE
Taklimakan Desert silts							
T-3	40.67	87.61	0.985	-9.7	0.2	0.717169	17
T-5	39.86	88.40	0.989	-9.0	0.2	0.716542	18
T-6	39.34	88.24	0.997	-9.5	0.2	0.716441	22
T-16	38.04	83.07	0.995	-10.0	0.2	0.717391	18
T-18	39.07	83.66	0.993	-9.1	0.2	0.716613	18
T-19	39.55	83.97	0.991	-8.7	0.1	0.717158	15
T-27	40.25	81.06	0.985	-9.5	0.1	0.717511	17
T-28	39.70	80.98	0.985	-8.7	0.1	0.717741	20
T-29	39.14	80.95	0.993	-8.9	0.2	0.717660	22
T-30	38.61	80.97	0.995	-8.6	0.2	0.717361	19
T-31	38.09	80.62	0.992	-9.0	0.1	0.717589	17
T-39	38.74	77.35	0.993	-10.5	0.2	0.715473	19
T-40	39.46	78.09	0.989	-8.5	0.1	0.716396	19
Eastern Kunlun Shan							
TG12-R05	39.20	89.51	0.992	-9.2	0.1	0.718958	11
TG12-R07	37.96	84.44	0.988	-10.2	0.1	0.717456	11
TG12-R08	37.49	84.29	0.962	-8.8	0.1	0.716831	15
TG12-R09	37.60	83.73	0.984	-9.9	0.1	0.718705	10
TG12-R10	37.33	83.18	0.977	-9.2	0.1	0.717133	13
TG12-R11	36.92	82.65	0.972	-9.3	0.1	0.718756	14
TG12-R12	36.46	81.48	0.966	-9.7	0.1	0.715882	10
TG12-R18	36.92	80.80	0.983	-8.6	0.1	0.717308	11
Qarqan-10	37.61	86.22	0.981	-9.9	0.1	0.716208	14
Western Kunlun Shan							
TG12-R19	36.89	79.60	0.961	-10.2	0.1	0.722181	11
TG12-R20	37.21	78.50	0.995	-12.3	0.1	0.722152	20
TG12-R21	38.03	77.33	0.985	-10.8	0.1	0.717637	11
TK-34R	37.26	79.16	0.976	-10.6	0.1	0.717876	16
TK-29R	37.82	77.45	0.984	-10.0	0.1	0.715582	14
Pamir Mountains							
TG12-R23	38.49	76.79	0.978	-9.9	0.1	0.715169	12
TG12-R24	38.64	76.17	0.980	-10.5	0.1	0.719069	14
TG12-R25	39.45	75.92	0.972	-10.0	0.1	0.714592	11
TK-25R	38.26	77.28	0.986	-10.5	0.1	0.714934	15
Tian Shan							
TG12-R13	41.78	83.50	0.960	-9.6	0.1	0.715051	11
TG12-R28	39.71	76.14	0.966	-10.7	0.1	0.719619	12
TG12-R29	39.85	76.99	0.961	-11.2	0.1	0.715912	6
TG12-R30	40.49	79.33	0.956	-12.5	0.1	0.720089	9
TG12-R31	41.19	80.09	0.956	-11.6	0.1	0.719890	16

TG12-R32	41.24	80.10	0.973	-10.8	0.1	0.715967	12
TG12-R33	41.69	82.69	0.969	-10.1	0.1	0.717384	8
TG12-R02	41.33	86.25	0.982	-9.9	0.1	0.716519	14
TG12-R34	42.00	83.06	0.935	-9.9	0.1	0.716196	14
Kunlun Shan loess							
KLS-1	36.20	81.34	0.987	-9.4	0.1	0.717271	12
YT1609	36.46	81.98	0.983	-9.1	0.1	0.717465	9
YT1608	36.47	81.93	0.988	-9.5	0.2	0.716747	11
CL1606A	36.06	81.08	0.991	-9.4	0.1	0.717305	9
CL1610	36.14	80.42	0.986	-9.0	0.1	0.717238	11
YT1601	36.17	81.47	0.990	-9.4	0.1	0.716945	11

Table 2. The ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) of >100 μm coarse particles and 20 – 25 μm fraction of freshly breaking particles.

Sample ID	Coarse particles	Freshly breaking particles
	($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) 2*SE = 0.001	($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) 2*SE = 0.001
T-19	1.012	1.015
T-18	1.010	1.012
T-30	1.012	1.012
T-31	1.007	1.010
Mean $\pm$ SE	1.010 $\pm$ 0.002	1.012 $\pm$ 0.001

Table 3. The U concentration of the 20 – 25 μm of the mountainous fluvial sediment samples and the TD silt samples.

Reservoir Num.	(2)	(3)
Materials	Mountain-derived silts (n=7)	TD silts (n=5)
U concentration (ppm) $\pm$ SE	3.20 $\pm$ 0.37	3.34 $\pm$ 0.20